

Temperature-Dependent Resistivity of Alternative Metal Thin Films

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Abstract—The temperature coefficient of resistivity (TCR) has been measured for Cu, Ru, Co, and Ir thin films with thicknesses down to 3 nm to assess the dominant electron scattering mechanism in these films. Ru, Co, and Ir show bulk-like TCR values down to 5 nm with some signs of disorder-induced TCR lowering for 3 nm for Ru and Co. By contrast, Cu shows a considerably larger TCR value than bulk that increases with decreasing thickness. The results are qualitatively consistent with calculations of the TCR within a semiclassical model.

Keywords—temperature coefficient of the resistivity; thin films; Cu; Ru; Ir; Co; semiclassical resistivity modeling

I. INTRODUCTION

Alternatives to the conventional Cu metallization in interconnects have been increasingly researched in recent years to mitigate the rapid increase in resistance and degraded reliability for sub-15 nm line and via widths [1-3]. The increase in interconnect and via resistance is due to scaling limitations of the barrier and liner layers required for reliable Cu metallization as well as to an increase in Cu resistivity as a result of enhanced surface and grain boundary scattering [1]. Recently, this has led to the integration of Co in local interconnects [4].

In this context, the TCR of metallic nanostructures is of interest both from a fundamental and an applied point of view. Numerous models have been developed to describe the additional scattering of the charge carriers due to surfaces and grain boundaries [5-9]. Semiclassical models [5] have seen widespread use since they allow for a rather simple quantitative fitting of experimental data. However, due to their simplicity and use of phenomenological parameters, their accuracy is still an open question. Measurements of *e.g.* the TCR can be used to test the applicability of such semiclassical models since temperature-dependent versions are available [10].

Moreover, temperature-dependent measurements of the resistance of interconnect lines have been widely used to extract simultaneously their resistivity and the cross-sectional area by the so-called TCR method [11,12]. In this method, the TCR value of the line needs to be approximated by a known value, typically the bulk TCR value. At present, it is not clear whether such an approximation holds quantitatively in presence of strong surface and grain boundary scattering. In contrast to wires, the TCR of *thin films* can be determined accurately and therefore the comparison of measured TCR values with bulk reference values will shed some light on the effect of surface and grain boundary scattering on the TCR.

II. EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

All films were deposited by physical vapor deposition at room temperature on 300 mm SiO₂/Si wafers. Film thicknesses were in the range between 3 and 10 nm. Ru and Ir were directly deposited on SiO₂, whereas Co and Cu were sandwiched between 1.5 nm thick TaN layers, deposited *in situ*, to avoid oxidation in air. The parallel conductance of the TaN layers was negligible in all measurements below. All films were polycrystalline with strong (111) and (001) fiber texture for the fcc (Cu, Ir) and hcp (Co, Ru) metals, respectively. AFM rms roughnesses were ~3 Å for all films. The temperature-dependent resistivity was determined using patterned Hall bars between room temperature and 125°C. The resistivity was found to increase linearly with temperature, indicating the TCR value showed no temperature dependence in the studied temperature window.

III. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Figure 1 shows the measured TCR values for Co, Ru, and Ir thin films as a function of their thickness. For comparison, the range of bulk TCR reference values as in [13] are also shown. Ir thin films showed bulk TCR values even for the thinnest film. Ru also showed values that fall in the bulk TCR range for thicknesses above 5 nm, whereas Co showed in this thickness range values are about 10% higher than those reported for bulk. The discrepancy between measured and reported Co TCR values is currently not fully understood. It cannot be excluded that it stems from systematic errors in the thickness dependence of the Co sandwiched between the TaN layers. However, the accuracy of the reported bulk Co TCR values in [13] to experimental Co thin films or wires still needs further consideration.

The TCR of both Co and Ru was found to decrease significantly for 3 nm thick films. This decrease might be attributed to strong disorder in the films, possibly due to large disordered grain boundary densities or interface layers with high point defect densities. As pointed out in [13], in strongly disordered materials, Matthiessen's rule ceases to be valid, leading to a reduction of the TCR in parallel with an increase of the resistivity. The TCR has been reported to become even negative above the Mott-Ioffe-Regel limit for metallic conductors [13]. The experimentally observed decrease for Ru and Co was however only ~10 to 15%, which indicates that disorder effects are weak and their contribution to the resistivity increase is not expected to be dominant. However, this suggests that such disorder effects might need to be included in resistivity models for extremely scaled metallic nanostructures.

Fig. 1. Experimental TCR values for Co, Ru, and Ir thin films as a function of the film thickness. The respective ranges of bulk TCR values as in [13] are shown for reference.

Figure 2 shows the experimental TCR for Cu vs. the film thickness. In contrast to Ru, Co, and Ir, Cu showed a significant increase of the TCR with decreasing thickness. At 10 nm, the TCR was slightly above the bulk reference value from [13] and increased by about 50% for the 3 nm film. This behavior can be attributed to the contribution of surface scattering to the resistivity in these films, as discussed in the next section. This suggests that the applicability of the TCR method to extremely scaled Cu wires might become increasingly doubtful and extracted areas might need to be verified by physical characterization means.

IV. SEMICLASSICAL MODEL OF THE TCR

The thickness dependence of the TCR can be assessed based on the semiclassical model of Mayadas and Shatzkes [5,10]. In this model, the film resistivity of a thin film with thickness h and linear intercept length between grain boundaries g is given by

$$\rho_{\text{tf}} = \left[\frac{1}{\rho_{\text{gb}}} - \frac{6}{\pi\kappa\rho_0} (1-p) \int_0^{\pi/2} d\phi \int_1^{\infty} dt \frac{\cos^2\phi}{H^2} \right. \\ \left. \times \left(\frac{1}{t^3} - \frac{1}{t^5} \right) \frac{1 - e^{-\kappa H t}}{1 - p e^{-\kappa H t}} \right]^{-1} \quad (1)$$

with

$$\rho_{\text{gb}} = \rho_0 [1 - 3\alpha/2 + 3\alpha^2 - 3\alpha^3 \ln(1 + 1/\alpha)]^{-1} \\ H = 1 + \alpha / \cos\phi \sqrt{(1 - 1/t^2)} \\ \alpha = (\lambda/g) \times [2R/(1 - R)] \\ \kappa = h/\lambda$$

Here, ρ_0 is the bulk resistivity of the metal and λ the mean free path of the charge carriers. The parameter p describes surface scattering with $p = 0$ for fully diffuse and $p = 1$ for specular scattering. The grain boundary reflection coefficient R describes the strength of grain boundary scattering. Equation (1) does not depend explicitly on temperature but via ρ_0 and λ . However, it has been argued that the product of ρ_0 and λ depends only on the morphology of the Fermi surface and should therefore be independent of temperature for metals in the range up to room temperature [15,16]. In nonmagnetic metals, the bulk resistivity is described by the Bloch-Grüneisen law

$$\rho_0(T) = \rho_0(0) + CT^5 \int_0^{\Theta_D} \frac{x^5}{(e^x - 1)(1 - e^{-x})} dx \quad (2)$$

with Θ_D the Debye temperature of the metal. Values of $\rho_0 \times \lambda$ have been calculated for numerous elemental metals [15]. This approach has been used to derive an approximate analytical model in [10]; it is however typically more convenient to calculate $\rho_{\text{tf}}(T)$ and the TCR numerically. The results can then be compared to experimental results to shed light on the effect of the different scattering contributions to the TCR and $\rho_{\text{tf}}(T)$.

Figure 3a shows the calculated TCR for Cu as a function of film thickness using parameters ($p = 0, R = 0.2$) determined from the experimental thickness dependence of the resistivity at room temperature [16] and assuming $g = 10$ nm [16]. The mean free path λ has also been taken from [16]. Above ~ 10 nm, the TCR was independent of thickness and equal to the bulk value. For thinner films, the TCR increased with decreasing thickness, similar to the experimental observations in Fig. 2. For a 3 nm thick film, the calculated TCR was about 15% larger than the bulk value. The calculated TCR of Ru using also parameters ($p = 0, R = 0.5$) determined from the thickness dependence of the resistivity, is shown in Fig. 3b. In contrast to Cu, the TCR of Ru was independent of film thickness and equal to the bulk value, in good qualitative agreement with the experimental results. The decrease of the TCR at the smallest thickness attributed to the breakdown of Matthiessen's rule due to disorder cannot be described within the semiclassical model and was therefore not reproduced in the calculations.

The strong difference in the behavior of Cu and Ru can be attributed to different dominant scattering mechanisms in the thin films. As discussed in [16], the Ru thin film resistance is determined by grain boundary scattering. Under such conditions, calculations of the TCR always find bulk values within the semiclassical model outlined above. However, as also argued in [16], in very thin Cu films, surface scattering can also contribute strongly to the resistivity due to the small R and the comparatively large λ . Therefore, it can be concluded that within the semiclassical model, the TCR is bulk like in the case when surface scattering is negligible. If surface scattering cannot be neglected, the TCR is larger than in the bulk. This conclusion is supported

Fig. 2. Experimental TCR values for Cu thin films as a function of the film thickness. The range of bulk TCR values as in [14] is shown for reference.

Fig. 3. Calculated thickness dependence of the TCR using the model described in the text for (a) Cu thin films and (b) Ru thin films.

by additional TCR calculations as a function of p as discussed in [12]. This picture is also in good agreement with the experimental results for Ir and Co. In both cases, R values are rather large [16,17] with respect to Cu and grain boundary scattering is dominating. As a result, bulk TCR values are found in the calculations (not shown), in keeping with the experimental results. It should however be noted that the calculated increase of the Cu TCR ($\sim 15\%$) at 3 nm thickness was significantly smaller than the experimental one ($\sim 50\%$). Thus, the semiclassical model can only qualitatively explain the observations. The underestimation of the ultrathin Cu TCR might be a hint that the approximations used to derive semiclassical models (and in particular the model in [5]) might not be fully valid, especially the assumption of a 3D free electron gas.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, the room-temperature TCR of Cu, Co, Ru, and Ir thin films has been experimentally studied and compared to calculations within a semiclassical model [5]. Good qualitative agreement between experimental results and calculations has generally been observed. This might indicate that the semiclassical models capture the essential “physics” of the transport. For Ru, Co, and Ir, the TCR is bulk-like, which can be attributed to the dominance of grain boundary scattering in these films, in keeping with the analysis of the thickness dependence [16,17]. For Cu, the TCR was found to increase significantly over the bulk value when the thickness decreased below 10 nm due to strong surface scattering contributions to the resistivity. This suggests that the application of the TCR method to extremely scaled Cu interconnect lines might increasingly underestimate the cross-sectional area of the lines. However, the semiclassical model failed to explain the experimental results in two aspects. First, the experimental increase of the Cu TCR at the thinnest films was clearly underestimated although the order of magnitude was roughly comparable. This is consistent with reported issues to

consistently describe Cu thin resistivity at variable temperature using semiclassical models [18] and sheds doubt on the usage of semiclassical models for the fully quantitative description of thin film resistivities. Moreover, semiclassical models cannot describe the experimentally observed reduction of the Ru and Co TCR below bulk values that can be attributed to the breakdown of Matthiessen’s rule due to disorder. This indicates that future quantitative models for thin film or nanowire resistivities might need to consider such effects.

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